

POORNAPRAJNA INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT

Accredited by NAAC with A+ (3.32 CGPA)

(Managed by Udupi ShreeAdamaruMatha Education Council)

One day National Conference on
Emerging trends in Management and Information Technology

Book of Abstracts

Date: 29 June 2024

Venue: Poornaprajna Institute of Management Udupi

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With the blessings of
His Holiness Shree Shree Eeshapriyathreetha Swamiji
President, USAMEC, Bengaluru,

One day National Conference on “Emerging Trends in Management and Information Technology” and Research Paper Presentation

is being organized at institution On 29 June 2024, Saturday.

Keynote Speakers

Dr. K.V.M. Varambally
Former Director & Professor
School of Management
MAHE, Manipal

Dr. Karunakar Kotegar
Professor
Dept. of Data Science & Computer
Application, MIT, Manipal

Inauguration of the conference will be held at 10.00AM

Chief Guest : **Dr. G. S. Chandrashekar**
Secretary, Poornaprajna Institute of Management

Guest of Honour: **CA. T. Prashantha Holla**
Treasurer, Poornaprajna Institute of Management

President : **Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal**
Director, PIM & Poornaprajna Group of Institutions

Venue: Prajna Hall, PIM.

All are cordially invited

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Consultant Service Quality in Construction Business

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study is to determine whether service quality practices impact client satisfaction and whether the report quality, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and professional expertise are significant in determining client satisfaction in consulting services in Nepal.

The study used structured questionnaire techniques for collecting client's perception. The study is based on descriptive research design. This study used quantitative method for data collection for the purpose of analysis. Mainly structured questionnaire survey was used to generate responses based on which statistical analysis is done to test hypothesis. The sampling technique for the study followed convenience sampling. For the analysis of collected data, statistical tests such as Correlation, ANOVA and Regression were conducted.

The major findings of this research document are: there exists positive relationship between report quality, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and professional expertise and client satisfaction. Hypothesis test also inferred that there is significant relationship between service quality practices and client satisfaction.

The study shows that the service provided by consultants is quite late compare to the time they promised. From the study following recommendations were suggested: client should provide the prompt and quick service, consultants should be trained enough to give the right answer of all the queries shown by the client, consulting firms should focus on its policies, procedures and clients' needs at the same time, safety of client should be enhanced and consulting firms should include a regular meeting in order to address clients need.

Keywords: Professional expertise, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, report quality, satisfaction.